

**A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY ON THE EXTENT OF COLLABORATION
ON PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT BETWEEN SPECIAL EDUCATION
TEACHERS AND PARENTS TO STUDENTS WITH
LEARNING DISABILITIES**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 8

Pages: 1006-1012

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2408

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13837889

Manuscript Accepted: 03-23-2023

A Phenomenological Study on the Extent of Collaboration on Psychosocial Support Between Special Education Teachers and Parents to Students with Learning Disabilities

Hanna Camille F. Pasion,* Wiltzhire Elle Alta T. Capulong, Leight Ashley A. Carandang,
Angelo A. Castillo, Trisha Khae Policarpio

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of this phenomenological study is to discover the lived experiences of the special education teachers and parents in terms of providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. Five (5) parents of children with learning disabilities (LD) and Five (5) special education teachers were chosen to be interviewed individually. Moreover, this study utilized a qualitative methodology to be able to gather in-depth data into and understanding the phenomenon. The result of this study has shown that majority of the parents of children with learning disabilities and special education teachers collaborate effectively through interaction and exchanging of feedbacks to maintain their engagement with one another and to consistently guide the child towards growth and development.

Keywords: *collaboration, learning disabilities, parent involvement, psychosocial support special education*

Introduction

Parents and special education teachers must collaborate to ensure a positive impact on a child's academic, behavioral, and socio-emotional development. Parental involvement is essential to the decision-making process and helps to determine the path of every child with special needs. Special education teachers serve as a guidance and source of special education information for parents to guide them through the overall process. The collaboration of parents and special education teachers is essential for providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. This collaboration can create strategies to strengthen the weaknesses of children with learning disabilities and build a support system to assist them in terms of their academic performance, development, and social skills. However, hindrances that may cause problems with their collaboration must be prevented to ensure effective psychosocial support. This study addressed the collaboration of parents and special education teachers by gathering in-depth information about their lived experiences regarding their collaboration and how it is beneficial for them and the children with learning disabilities.

Research Questions

This study aims to know the lived experiences on the extent of collaboration of the Special Education teachers and Parents on Psychosocial Support to Students with Learning Disabilities Specifically, the researchers have sought to answer the following:

1. What are the lived experiences of the special education teachers and parents in terms of their extent of collaboration in providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities?
2. Why is the extent of collaboration on psychosocial support important between special education teachers and parents of students with learning disabilities?
3. How does the extent of collaboration on psychosocial support benefit special education teachers and parents of students with learning disabilities?
4. What are the interventions that can be proposed to continuously improve the system of collaboration on psychosocial support between special education teachers and parents of students with learning disabilities?

Literature Review

Collaboration is essential for involving parents in the special education process and can serve as the basis for collaboration and information sharing. Special education (SPED) teachers must better understand how they present special education information to parents and support parents in acquiring knowledge before they can fully realize their role as parents as a guidance through the special education process of their child. It clearly shows the positive relationship between parental involvement in school and student achievement. As a parent of a special education student, such involvement depends on their understanding of programs and services, which can be influenced by teachers' collaboration and communication. Overall, teacher information is essential for parents to develop an understanding of special education, which serves as the foundation for parental involvement in their child's special needs and education (Farley et al., 2022).

In the recent study conducted by Baykal et al. (2020), it has been revealed that collaboration between parents and special education (SPED) teachers is a wide range of utilization such as in cooperation, group skills, and social interaction. Moreover, this study shows that these approaches are what is often used in the system of the collaboration parents and special education (SPED) teachers to be able to attend to every child's special needs.

The partnership between the family and school is vital in testing student behaviors and addressing the children's behavioral concerns. In the study by Semke and Sheridan (2012), effectively strengthening the collaboration between parents and teachers is evident. It also

examined the family and school partnership in promoting the adaptive and positive behaviors of children with learning disabilities both at school and at home. In addition, it has been proven that conjoint behavioral consultation for students shows more significant improvements in social skills than those not receiving any treatments with the help of cooperative plan intervention, mutual goal setting, and joint planning.

The collaboration of parents and special education (SPED) teachers is incredibly important to further assist students with special needs. Also, it is evident that the roles of parents and teachers in providing special needs have benefits not only to children inside the classroom but also for parents and teachers since it increases their effectiveness in terms of their collaboration. Differences in views of parents and teachers provide insights concerning how the collaboration takes place and how they can offer the best creative ways to accomplish their goals of bringing better outcomes for children, especially those with special educational needs (Adams et al., 2016).

Utilizing communication between the parents and teachers is vital for the child's success. For instance, in the study of Stone (2021), special education (SPED) teachers always communicate with their student's parents to share information about every child's need to be successful at home and their child's day. Also, it is essential to maintain a positive relationship between them to ensure that the child's needs are met at the end of the day. Teachers communicate with parents via email, phone, text, mail, other apps, or personally, like attending school meetings. They even make communication binders to keep track of the records of every student for parents to see and maintain communication.

As stated in the study by Javier and Jubay (2019), Parents and teachers are united in their goals for their children and students; they want every individual to do their best not only to complete their studies but also to achieve better in every discipline. That is why improving and identifying factors to improve the collaboration of parents' and teachers' is a good steppingstone to producing better outcomes. It can happen in diverse ways, such as maintaining better communication between parents and teachers.

Based on the study conducted by Paccaud et al. (2021), the results have shown that they offer schools ways to improve their work for the collaboration between the parents and teachers, such as schools can equip support systems to assist parents in coping with their struggles in daily life. Also, families can help them to be a resource for a suitable environment to offer optimal learning for children and development opportunities. In that way, both parties can build a connection and create a powerful team to provide children with their special educational needs.

Positive collaboration between parents and teachers has been revealed to improve emotional well-being, children's academic achievement, and social competencies (Ludvik, 2020). Parents' and teachers' collaboration is proven to create benefits that would really help children, especially those with learning disabilities, in terms of their social skills and adaptability to situations, attitudes, and behaviors. Parents attend meetings and observe everything to let the teachers know their child's efforts and behaviors, which shows that they care about the well-being of their children. Also, parents and teachers benefit because it builds a healthy relationship that would enable them to develop skills to support children's learning and behaviors. In addition, to effectively communicate and maintain their collaboration.

In accordance with Karibayeva and Boğar (2014), parents and teachers are both significant in children's academic life. Parent involvement does not mean anything shallow but more like participating in school meetings and events, communicating with teachers, and attending to their child's needs at home. Also, their participation in the children's life is one of the many factors that can aid in improving their behavior, progress, language abilities, social skills, and life in general

Communication between parents and special education teachers is vital to help students discover their potential. Ozmen et al. (2016) state that barriers should be eliminated to communicate well with one another. Mutual trust and tolerance should be practiced increasing their healthy relationship. In addition, schools should build preventive factors to develop efficient communication and how to overcome those barriers to reach the effectiveness of collaboration between parents and teachers. Besides, teachers should consider the cultural differences and socio-economic of the parents' environments to enhance communication and avoid miscommunication between them since it might affect the children.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used this study will be based on a correlational-descriptive type of research study, with this, the researchers will have an in-depth understanding and statistical results regarding the extent of collaboration between the parents and special education (SPED) teachers on psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. As stated by Judith Quaranta (2017), A descriptive correlational study is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection

Respondents

The table illustrates the demographic profile of the special education (SPED) teachers and parents of students with learning disabilities. Moreover, this table showed that most of the parents were female and majority of them only had one (1) child diagnosed with a learning disability. On the other hand, the years of teaching experience of these special education (SPED) teachers was 4 to 5 years, while

participant 4 already has 12 years of teaching experience.

Table 1. *Summary of the Demographic Profile of Parents and Special Education (SPED) Teachers*

<i>Parent Participant number</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Number of Children with Learning Disabilities</i>
1	F	1
2	F	1
3	F	1
4	F	1
5	F	1
<i>SPED Teacher Participant number</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Number of Working Experience in the Field of Special Education</i>
6	F	4 years
7	F	4 years
8	F	5 years
9	F	12 years
10	F	5 years

Instrument

The researchers conducted an interview face-to-face since the lockdown had been lifted. Besides, gathering information when talking personally with the participants is more effective because this will help the researchers have ample time to discuss with them and gather data based on their phenomenological experiences. The interview was done through an individual interview with 10 participants, five (5) parents and five (5) Special Education (SPED) teachers within the learning institution, wherein the interviewers will ask questions to the participants to know their perspectives, beliefs, and approach to be able to gather a variety of information (Bojlen & Lunde, 1995).

The researchers constructed seven (7) semi-structured questions for the selected participants in order for the researchers to discover their experiences, such as their challenges and strategic approach in terms of providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities.

Procedure

The researchers asked permission to submit a permission letter to the principal of the Governor D. M. Integrated School in Imus Cavite that allowed the researchers to conduct the survey and the interview. Furthermore, the researchers have conducted an individual interview to ask the seven (7) semi-structured interview questions to be asked for the parents and special education teacher.

Ethical Considerations

This study enlists the respondents' consent form in line with R.A #10173 or the Data Privacy Policy Act of 2012. It is an act of protecting an individual's personal information and communications systems in the school. To ensure the safety of the respondents, in addition to this, they also have the right to back out anytime they would like before and during the interview.

Results and Discussion

Table 2.

<i>Interview Question</i>	<i>Cluster Theme 1</i>	<i>Emergent Theme 1</i>
1. "As a parent/special education (SPED) teacher of a student with a learning disability, to what extent of collaboration on psychosocial support do you do to engage with the parent/special education (SPED) teacher? In what specific ways do you collaborate?"	Communication	Importance of Communication on the Extent of Collaboration

Parents and special education (SPED) teachers asserted that communication is their way to collaborate with one another. Moreover, through their communication it helps the child create progress at school and at home in terms of their learning and socialization skills and development. In accordance with Javier & Jubay (2019), there is a collaboration between the parent of a student with a learning disability and the special education teacher that can be seen through communication, explicitly informing each other about the child's academic progress inside the institution and at home. And having the same goal of providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. The extent of collaboration is to yield better outcomes on the child's achievements in every discipline.

Table 3.

<i>Interview Question</i>	<i>Cluster Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
2. "What do you think are the hindrances that you have experienced in terms of your extent of collaboration with a special education teacher when providing psychosocial support to your child with a learning disability?"	Hindrance	Barriers and Issues on the Extent of Collaboration

When it comes with the collaboration of the parents and special education (SPED) teachers it has revealed that due to lack of special education teachers and their busy schedules, it hinders the process of their collaboration, therefore having less engagement with one another and difficulty of compromising with the child's situation within the institution and at home. And as stated by Allam and Martin (2021), the hindrances to the collaboration with the special education teachers are the schedules, the curriculum guide, and the lack of special education (SPED) teachers. In addition, based on the study of Hernandez (2013), since there are usually less special education (SPED) teachers and busy schedules of the parents as well, this causes problems with their collaboration such as less time for engagement which hinders their mutually agreed upon goals for the child with special needs and their communication would reduce for a short period of time having less engagement with one another.

Table 4.

<i>Interview Question</i>	<i>Cluster Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
3. "How do you benefit from the extent of your collaboration when providing psychosocial support to a child with a learning disability?"	Beneficial factors	The Strength of the Extent on Collaboration between Parents and Special Education (SPED) teachers

With the collaboration of parents and special education (SPED) teachers in terms of providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities (LD), it gives them the benefit to widen their partnership and knowledge for they provide information and feedback to one another in effectively managing the child. As claimed by Ozmen et al. (2016), interaction between parents and special education teachers is crucial. Through communication, it reaches the effectiveness and are able to meet the goal for the child's development when communication is continuously done between parents and special education teachers. Furthermore, through communication, special needs of children with learning disabilities will be met; parents and special education teachers just needs to build connection to be able to share information consistently.

Table 5.

<i>Interview Question</i>	<i>Cluster Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
4. Why do you think it is important to have an extent of collaboration with the special education teachers in terms of providing psychosocial support to students with learning disabilities?	Interpersonal approach and Knowledge	Understanding and Reliability of SPED Teachers within the process on the extent of collaboration with parents

The collaboration of parents and teachers are important for the improvement of the child's performance and well-being. They work together to understand their child's psychosocial needs and devise strategies to attend to them and as stated in the study conducted by Adams and Jones (2016), the collaboration between parents and teachers is incredibly important to further assist students with special needs. Also, it is evident that the roles of parents and teachers in providing special needs have benefits not only to children inside the classroom but also for parents and teachers since it increases their effectiveness in terms of their collaboration.

Table 6.

<i>Interview Question</i>	<i>Cluster Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
5. "In terms of communication, how would you maintain a positive relationship with the Parent/Special Education teacher of your child in providing psychosocial support?"	Connectedness and Rapport	Vital interpersonal relationship among parents and SPED teachers

Open communication is crucial to maintain a positive relationship with one another in the extent of collaboration to provide adequate psychosocial support in terms of the child's performance, socialization skills, and mental well-being to children with learning disabilities. In addition, as stated by in the study conducted by Stone (2021), communication between the parents and teachers is vital for the child's success. The teachers always communicate with their student's parents to share information about every child's need to be successful at home and their child's day. Also, it is essential to maintain a positive relationship between them to ensure that the child's needs are met at the end of the day. Teachers communicate with parents via email, phone, text, mail, other apps, or personally, like attending school meetings. They even make communication binders to keep track of the records of every student for parents to see and maintain communication.

Table 7.

<i>Interview Question</i>	<i>Cluster Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
6. Why do you think it is important to have an extent of collaboration with the special education teachers in terms of providing psychosocial support to students with learning disabilities?	Learnings and Insights	Learnings within the collaboration of parents with SPED teacher/s

The teachings and practices contributed by parents and special education teachers assisted them in their collaboration as they offered the most appropriate psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities to reach the efficacy of the children's growth and development. As aligned in the study conducted by Adams et al. (2016), the collaboration between parents and teachers is incredibly

important to further assist students with special needs. Also, it is evident that the roles of parents and teachers in providing special needs have benefits not only to children inside the classroom but also for parents and teachers since it increases their effectiveness in terms of their collaboration. Differences in views of parents and teachers provide insights concerning how the collaboration takes place and how they can offer the best creative ways to accomplish their goals of bringing better outcomes for children, especially those with special educational needs.

Table 8.

<i>Interview Question</i>	<i>Cluster Theme</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>
7. Why do you think it is important to have an extent of collaboration with the special education teachers in terms of providing psychosocial support to students with learning disabilities?	Engagement approach	Innovative approach of Parents and SPED Teachers on the extent of their Collaboration

The extent of collaboration between parents of students with learning disabilities and special education teachers shows the effectiveness. It is highly collaborative in providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. It gives them enough information by exchanging updates regarding the child's school and home performance. With this, they can monitor the child's development to devise a strategy for their psychosocial needs. The extent of collaboration between parents of students with learning disabilities and special education teachers shows the effectiveness. It is highly collaborative in providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. It gives them enough information by exchanging updates regarding the child's school and home performance. With this, they can monitor the child's development to devise a strategy for their psychosocial needs. In the study conducted by Farley et al. (2022), partnership is essential for involving parents in the special education process and can serve as the basis for collaboration and information sharing.

In line with the result, communication is the vital approach of parents and special education (SPED) teachers when providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. They monitor the child's progress in this way to observe developments in the child's performance as well as their behavior at school and home. However, there are still issues with their collaboration. Still, despite these hindrances, special education (SPED) educators and parents showed their eagerness to collaborate to consistently provide psychosocial support to these children with learning disabilities (LD) to further help improve the child's performance and well-being.

Collaboration is a significant method that is utilized in collaboration in terms of providing psychosocial support to children with learning disabilities. This is because through their interaction it benefits them and the children with a positive outcome of the child's development on their performance and behavior at school and at home (Javier and Jubay, 2019). Moreover, as for the hindrances in their collaboration such as the busy schedule of working parents, it revealed that it limits their engagement with the SPED teachers. Also, some parents experience difficulty in accepting their child's condition (Choi and Ostendorf, 2015). On the other hand, special education teachers experience less time engagement with the parents of their students with learning disabilities. And lack of special education teachers (Obare, 2019) to be able to attend to collaborate with the parents (Farley et al, 2022). Lastly, even though they experience barriers in terms of their collaboration, parents and special education teachers are important to a child's development (Ludwik, 2020). With this, parents and special education teachers are still collaborative to be able to guide and provide psychosocial support for the child with a learning disability to continuously improve their behavior, performance, and social skills (Karibeyeya and Bogar, 2014); (Balli, 2016).

Conclusions

Below are the following conclusions drawn based on the outcome of the study:

Importance of communication on the extent of collaboration: communication is essential for successful collaboration between special education teachers and parents, especially in providing updates and feedback to one another regarding the child's situation and condition at school and at home.

Barriers and issues on the extent of collaboration: There are situations wherein the collaboration is being hindered due to time constraint with the busy schedules of the special education teachers and less parent involvement due to lack of knowledge on their child's condition, busy schedule of the parents, financial difficulties, transportation problems, and difficulty for parents in accepting their child's condition.

The strength of the collaboration of parents and special education (SPED) teachers: Despite the hindrances, parents and special education (SPED) teachers showed eagerness within their collaboration to be able to continuously guide and provide support throughout the child's growth and development. for them to have a positive mental well-being and to be able to enhance themselves more in all areas of their behavior, attitude, and performance at school and at home in the course of time.

Reliability of special education (SPED) teachers and parents within the process on the extent of collaboration: Both special education (SPED) teachers and parents were dependable to one another, because within their collaboration they monitor the child's progress and provide the information to one another consistently as well as sharing important details with the child's behavior for them to both be aware on how they can effectively manage the child.

Vital positive partnership among parents and special education (SPED) teachers in terms of their collaboration: Through their collaboration, the parents and special education (SPED) teachers maintains their positive partnership by communication through exchanging of feedbacks and providing information to one another to monitor the child's progress, sharing tips and advice. As for their other approaches to maintain the said partnership, is that they show compassion, honesty, and owe their roles and responsibilities in their collaboration.

Learnings within the collaboration of parents and special education (SPED) teachers: Majority of the special education (SPED) teachers and parents' advantage in terms of their collaboration is learning to one another based on how they handle the child at school and at home.

Innovative approaches of parents and special education (SPED) teachers on the extent of their collaboration: With parents and special education (SPED) teachers, most of their propound contributions is to share information based from a mental health professionals' perspective that can help and provide psychosocial support to a child with a learning disability (LD) and conduct support groups for them and the students with learning disabilities (LDs).

References

- Adams, D., Harris, A., & Jones, M.S., (2016). Teacher-Parent Collaboration for an Inclusive Classroom: Success for Every Child. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1106456.pdf>
- Allam, F. C., & Martin, M. M. (2021). Issues and Challenges in Special Education: A Qualitative Analysis from Teacher's Perspective. *Southeast Asia Early Childhood Journal*, 10(1), 37-49. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1296259.pdf>
- Baykal, G. E., Van Mechelen, M., & Eriksson, E. (2020). Collaborative Technologies for Children with Special Needs. Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. <https://sci-hub.ru/https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3313831.3376291>
- Choi, N. & Ostendorf, R. (2014, November 30). Perceptions of Disability and Special Education Services: The Perspectives of Korean-American Parents of Children with Disabilities. *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1134156>
- Farley J., et al. (2022). Teacher Perspectives on Information Sharing and Parent Knowledge of Special Education. EJ1336505.pdf (ed.gov)
- Hernandez, S. J. (2013). Collaboration in Special Education: Its History, Evolution, and Critical Factors Necessary for Successful Implementation. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED544122>
- Javier, D. R. C., Jubay, R. P. (2019, September). Exploring Parent-Teacher Collaboration To Improve Students' Vocabulary Skills: An Action Research. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336135123_Exploring_Parent-Teacher_Collaboration_To_Improve_Students'_Vocabulary_Skills_An_Action_Research
- Karibayeva, A., & Boğar, Y. (2014). To what Extent does Parents' Involvement in Middle School Influence Children's Educational Progress? <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.09.222>
- Ludvik, D. (2020, November 9). Establishing Healthy Parent-teacher Relationships for Early Learning Success. *Early Learning Network*. <https://earlylearningnetwork.unl.edu/2018/08/29/parent-teacher-relationships/>
- Ozmen, F. , Akuzum, C. , Zincirli, M. & Selcuk, G. (2016). The Communication Barriers between Teachers and Parents in Primary Schools . *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research* , 16 (66) , 27-46 . Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ejer/issue/42424/510769?fbclid=IwAR0nkdnWuvqenJ7sismPiYvZuknHESn82Ac>
- Paccaud, A., Keller, R., Luder, R., Pastore, G., & Kunz, A. (2021, March 4). Satisfaction with the Collaboration between Families and Schools – the Parent's View. *Frontiers*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2021.646878/full>
- Stone, T. (2021). The Role of Teachers and Parents for Students with Learning and Behavior Disorders. *Murray State University*. https://digitalcommons.murraystate.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1386&context=bis4_37
- Semke, C. A. & Sheridan, S. M. (2012). Family-school Connections in Rural Educational Settings: A Systematic Review of the Empirical Literature. *School Community Journal*, 22(1), 21-47. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ974684>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Hanna Camille F. Pasion

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Wiltzhire Elle Alta T. Capulong

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Leight Ashley A. Carandang

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Angelo A. Castillo

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Trisha Khae Policarpio

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines